

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 4.6 to AD4.1 – Urine Sampling Questionnaire for Children (6 – 11 years)

WP 4

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Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
Version 1	2023-06-22	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr; Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	
Version 2	2023-07-11	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr; Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	Small adaptations after external review of AD4.1
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U.01: Question for fieldworker about urine sample collection

Q120: Has the urine sample been delivered?

Yes

No

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q120.1: Please indicate the reason for missing submission of the urine sample

Sampling container not available

No consent

Other reason

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q120.1.1: Other reason, that being _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q121: Was the urine sample collected in the provided container?

Yes

No

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q122: Is there a sampling label on the container?

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q122.1: Is there a label with the correct participant id on the container?

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q129: Were there any peculiarities with the sample or participant's answers?

No

Yes

Refused to provide sample

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q129.1: Which ones? _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

I.00: Questionnaire information

Q093: Id (participant) _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q094: Id (interviewer) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q095: Date of the interview **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q095.1: Day _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q095.2: Month _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q095.3: Year _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q096: Start time **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q096.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q096.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q097: End time **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q097.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q097.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q098: Interview place / interview platform _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

U.02: Question for participant about urine sample collection

Q123: When was your child's urine sample obtained? **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q123.1: On **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q123.1.1: Day _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q123.1.2: Month _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q123.1.3: Year _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q123.2: At **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q123.2.1: Hour _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q123.2.2: Minute _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q124: Is it really the first urine after your child waking up?

No

Yes

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q124.1: Please indicate the reason for missing submission of the morning urine sample

Sampling was forgotten in the morning

Other reason

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q124.1.1: Other reason, that being _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q126: When did your child last urinate before urine sample collection (date and time)? **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q126.1: On **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q126.1.1: Day _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q126.1.2: Month _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q126.1.3: Year _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q126.2: At **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q126.2.1: Hour _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q126.2.2: Minute _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q127: How was your child's sample stored at home before collection?

Refrigerator

Other cool place

Non-chilled

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q128: Is your child's morning urine sample complete? Complete means that all morning urine - entire bladder emptying - was collected for the urine sample.

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q128.1: Please indicate the reason for incomplete morning urine sample

Forgot that all morning urine is collected

Something went wrong

The collection container was too small

Other reason

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q128.1.1: Other reason, that being _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q125: When was your child's last meal before urine sample collection? **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q125.1: On **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q125.1.1: Day _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q125.1.2: Month _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q125.1.3: Year _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q125.2: At (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q125.2.1: Hour _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q125.2.2: Minute _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

U.03: Recent exposure

Q146: Does your child drink tea (do not refer to herbal infusions)?

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q146.1: If the answer is yes, did your child drink the following types of tea during the 48 hrs prior to sampling?

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q146.1.1: Black tea

No

Yes

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q146.1.1.1: Total number of cups in the last 48hrs _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q146.1.2: Green tea

No

Yes

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q146.1.2.1: Total number of cups in the last 48hrs _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q147: Before providing the sample, when did your child last drink water from wells and artesian wells?

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

More than 48 hours ago

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q148: Has your child inhaled smoke from any of the following energy sources inside your home during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

Charcoal/coal

Wood (firewood, chips, pellets, etc.)

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q149: Has your child used insecticide products to control or repel insects (including treatment of pets) at your house in the 48 hours prior to sampling? Please, consider insecticide sprays, tablets, liquids etc...

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q150: Has your child used insect repellents or anti-parasite products for human use (e.G. Mosquitos, lice, ticks products...), during the past 48 hrs prior to sampling?

No

Yes

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q151: Has your garden/vegetable garden been treated with pesticides in the last week (7 days)?

- No
- Yes
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

UB.03: Recent exposure

Q138: Before providing the sample, when did your child last eat any food belonging to the following food groups?

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.1: White fish (e.G. Hake, snapper, sea bream, cod, haddock, grouper, halibut, tilapia, bass)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.2: Small oily fish (e.G. Anchovy, sardines, salmon)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.3: Big oily fish (e.G. Sword fish, tuna, school shark)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.4: Other seafood (e.G. Octopus, squid, shrimps, scampi)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.5: Meat (e.G. White and red meat, game, offal)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.6: Snails

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago

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Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.7: Rice

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.8: Other cereals (e.G. Bread, crackers, grains, pasta)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.9: Algae/seaweeds

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.10: Mushrooms

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.11: Vegetables (e.G. Potatoes, leafy vegetables)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.12: Fruits (e.G. Oranges, grapes, apples)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.13: Dairy products (e.G. Butter, milk, cheese)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

ANNEX 4.6 – URINE SAMPLING QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

Q138.14: Fats (animal, e.G. Lard and vegetal, e.G. Olive or sunflower oil)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.15: Potato chips (packaged)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.16: Microwave popcorn (cooked in bags)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.18: Peanuts

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.19: Chewing gum

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.20: Smoked food (e.G. Ham, smoked pork, smoked cheese, frankfurters)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.21: Canned food

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.22: Fast food

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- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.23: Ready meals (in plastic packaging)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q139: When did your child last take dietary supplements (algae, spirulina, vitamins, minerals, omega-3 fatty acids etc...) during the past 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- Not at all
- Less than 5 hours ago
- Between 5 and 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q139.1: If yes, please specify supplement _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q140: Before providing the sample, when did your child last drink any beverages belonging to the following list?

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q140.3: Whole milk

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q140.4: Vegetable/fruit juice (hand-made)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q140.5: Vegetable/fruit juice (processed)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q141: Has your child been exposed to tobacco smoke during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- No
- Yes, i have smoked
- Yes, i have been exposed to second hand smoke (passive smoking)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q141.2: How long has your child been exposed to secondhand smoking during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- Less than an hour

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- More than 1 hour
- More than 4 hours
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q142: Has your child been exposed to electronic cigarettes vapors during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- No
- Yes, i have vaped
- Yes, i have been exposed to secondhand vape smoke

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q142.2: How long has your child been exposed to secondhand vape smoke during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- Less than an hour
- More than 1 hour
- More than 4 hours
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q144: Did your child take any medicines during the past 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- No
- Yes

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q144.1: If yes, please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q145: During the past 24 hrs prior to sampling, did your child undergo one or more of the following medical treatments? Choose from the following options: **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q145.1: Intravenous (iv) infusion **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q145.3: Dialysis **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q145.4: Don't know **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**